

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D5.2 OUTREACH AND IMPACT CREATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

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Abstract	<i>This document describes STADIEM communication and community building strategy. It also presents the activities STADIEM deployed in the first four months of the project and the plan to guarantee broad visibility, promotion, and up-take of the STADIEM-driven activities. It dedicates a section to STADIEM liaison with relevant initiatives and networks at European and international level. This should be considered as a living document that reflects the emerging opportunities and changing conditions that apply according to the Next Generation Media ecosystem priorities and needs of a growing and 'on-the-move' community.</i>
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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the communication strategy and planning of STADIEM. This entails outlining the communicative approach of STADIEM to achieve its ambitions and support project partners in their daily activities.

It does so by firstly elaborating on what the main dissemination and promotion objectives are.

Secondly, this deliverable presents the foundation of the dissemination and promotion strategy and the identified primary projects' stakeholders who have been defined in the perspective of aligning the project's ambitions with the overall Next Generation Media (NGM) ecosystem and Next Generation Internet (NGI) vision and program-level community building and marketing activities.

- In relation to that, the deliverable goes on by presenting the set of means and actions that are (being) implemented in the first four months of the project. This includes the selection and set-up of communication channels to reach our target audiences. Then, the central part of this document presents the dissemination and communication plan envisaged for the next 32 months, including the initial discussions related to the exploitation and sustainability plan, which will be detailed in D5.6, D5.7 Market Analysis, Exploitation and Sustainability at M18 and M36.
- We conclude the deliverable with an overview of the quantitative and qualitative indicators that will be used to monitor the projects' communication and dissemination results, contributing to a precise assessment of STADIEM's impact.
- This document, which will evolve in line with the development of the overall project work and activities in close collaboration with all work packages, is written primarily as a guide for STADIEM project partners and key stakeholders in the Next Generation Media context to inform and explain communication and outreach activities.

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ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
NGI	Next Generation Internet
NGM	Next Generation Media
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 STADIEM IN A NUTSHELL

STADIEM aims to develop a strong community of (non-)tech & (non-)media stakeholders to stimulate, shape and foster the application of emerging technologies (e.g., 5G, cloud, the Internet of Things, virtual/augmented reality, smart objects, wearables, data analytics, artificial intelligence, etc.) on the NGM through the deployment of a dynamic and impactful incubation and acceleration program.

1.2 GROUNDING STADIEM OUTREACH AND IMPACT STRATEGY

Media and the creative industries play a key role in the European economy serving as the basis for European diversity, values, and democracies. In the words of Klossa, “the future of media and the future of democracy in Europe are intimately interwoven”. They account for 4.4% of the EU’s GDP and 12 million full-time jobs. However, they are also facing challenges. The industry in Europe is composed of many small companies and the virtual borders between countries are still very much present in the industry due to different cultures and/or languages, and industry structures and barriers.

The rise of the digital era has brought novel immersive, accessible, and personalized user experiences to media, thereby disrupting traditional media. Today, media form a complex ecosystem of users and producers, audiences, and performers with interchangeable roles where traditional boundaries of media are blurring. In this process, media have also become a key element in societal discourses.

Digitization and globalization are giving rise to considerable opportunities but at the same time pose challenges for the European media sector. Following the push from accelerated convergence, the radio and audiovisual sectors have become innovation-driven industries. Change is visible everywhere, from products and services, distribution and production processes to ownership and financing. The evolving positioning of users and the way we imagine the role of media in our societies are also playing a crucial role in this context.

STADIEM’s ambition is to contribute to identifying, nurturing, and retaining promising start-ups and connecting them with media industries by creating concrete opportunities to collaborate. Through an intense ecosystem analysis and continuous networking activities it aims to:

- facilitate the uptake of innovations by leveraging emerging technologies such as 5G, Cloud, the Internet of Things, Virtual/Augmented Reality, smart objects, wearables, data analytics, artificial intelligence, etc. in next generation media that overcome traditional boundaries and sectors,
- help the new media ecosystem become more adaptive and inclusive, and better promote content, e.g., with new online strategies and business models or new forms of content creation/distribution/presentation,
- support synergies across media, operators, technologists, and cultural/artistic actors, in order to develop a network of stakeholders, which will explore innovative paths for the next generation of media.

2 OUTREACH AND IMPACT CREATION STRATEGY

An efficient and effective dissemination and communication strategy can ensure short and long-term success of a project. Therefore, promotion, dissemination, exploitation and engagement activities are key to achieving impact with STADIEM. A comprehensive plan of activities will be closely coordinated among the various WPs to effectively engage all target stakeholders in the Next Generation Media ecosystem.

STADIEM will engage in dissemination, communication, and community building with investors/corporates, incubators and accelerators, SMEs and startups, researchers in industry and academia, cultural/artistic actors, innovators, media producers, operators, policy makers and users, as well as relevant NGM communities and projects as appropriate.

As STADIEM includes open calls throughout its duration, specific efforts will be dedicated to their promotion as detailed in section 2.3. Additionally, more information on open call promotion materials (already created and planned) can be found in section 4.7.

A comprehensive and well-structured set of dissemination activities are aimed to raise awareness and encourage uptake of developed concepts, technologies, use cases, and results. This will include offline and online communications, digital presence, participation in and organization of events, contributions to standardization, interactions and liaisons with relevant initiatives and projects.

The following sections describe STADIEM's mission, overall communication and dissemination objectives to achieve the project's ambitions, key stakeholders that need to be engaged, and related communication guidelines and channels that will inform and streamline STADIEM's communication and dissemination activities.

2.1 OBJECTIVES

STADIEM concept and methodology are built around four project Innovation Hubs as the core and starting point for a greater community that consists of several individual ecosystems and stakeholders from the media and non-media sectors (verticals). To ensure and maximize the success, effectiveness and impact of the incubation programme, as well as its future sustainability, deployment and expansion to new hubs in the European landscape, the establishment of a wider community in the Next Generation Media is of significant value. It is the main target of the project dissemination and communication plan and activities, and can be translated into the following distinct objectives:

- Ensure broad visibility and raise awareness about STADIEM, spreading knowledge about the project and its results, establishing a distinctive and recognizable identity that will support promotional and marketing efforts.
- Ensure participation of innovators in the STADIEM open calls (2)
- Reach, stimulate and engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to ensure that (a) the results of the project and 3rd party projects selected through STADIEM open calls are effectively showcased, leading to validation, improvement and possibly further adoption of the developed technologies and concepts; (b) the Open Calls and Incubation Programme of the project are effectively and properly disseminated to the targeted audiences for maximum participation and promotion.
- Facilitate exploitation of the project's outcomes and promote the development of innovative solutions based on the STADIEM technologies and concepts.

- To fully support the key players' engagement strategy in the project activities and concepts around the Open Calls and the Incubation Programme, while promoting and providing great visibility on the 3rd party projects and the best practices learned that will lead to the creation of a new business model in the media domain.
- Foster impactful contribution to relevant scientific domains and standardization bodies, as appropriate and relevant to planned exploitation plans and the project's outcomes.
- Establish strong liaisons and ensure close collaboration with relevant initiatives in the media industry and in the research and innovation domains.

2.2 STAKEHOLDERS

STADIEM plans to engage a wide expert and a network of key corporate players and venture partners in the media sector, to support and boost the possibilities for start-ups by providing access to large teams of mentors and coaches.

The innovation capacity and integration of new knowledge achieved by the proposition in STADIEM, has the potential to impact the stakeholders in the table below.

More details regarding the STADIEM stakeholders mapping and engagement are provided by D1.1 Community Building Strategy (M03) and D1.2 Community Map and database (M06).

This table presents the main message related to the impact expected on these groups of stakeholders, along with the first plan of activities based on the community building and outreach and impact creation plans during the implementation of the project.

TABLE 1 : STADIEM STAKEHOLDERS, KEY MESSAGES AND COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

TARGET	KEY MESSAGE	PLANNED ACTIVITIES	OBJECTIVES
Group: Traditional media, operators, media producers			
Traditional media stakeholders, operators and media producers	<i>Benefit from leveraging upon the advanced technological solutions and business models, liaise with innovators and greater NGM community</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Invitation to participate in workshops > Engage at specific events/workshops and exhibitions > Targeted publications and online communication 	Creating a community in the NGM ecosystem, towards long-term sustainability and further exploitation of project outcome
Group: Technologists and technology innovators			
Private companies, corporates, and technology & services providers	<i>Benefit and leverage upon the delivered results to create innovative solutions and new business models</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Invitation to participate in workshops > Engage at specific events/workshops and exhibitions 	Strengthen the long-term sustainability and technology uptake of funded innovators

		> Targeted publications and online communication	
Group: Cultural / artistic actors			
Artists, cultural organisations and institutes	<i>Liaise with innovators in the NGM domain, awareness on last achievements, contribute to the delivery of new / advanced processes / tools in NGM</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Engage with innovators at specific events/workshops > Targeted publications and online communication > Engage at specific events/workshops and exhibitions 	Enriching the community with artistic and cultural aspects /perspectives, as well as with scopes and collaboration opportunities
Group: SMEs and startups			
Startups, SMEs	<i>Benefit from NGM related solutions and combined technologies and resources to minimize up time-to-market for their applications and services – increased market visibility and liaisons with industry and build new business models</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Promote outputs (newsletters, social media, news, blogs, reports) and their possible uptake - B2B > Engage with innovators at specific events/workshops > Give voice to SME/Start-up representatives (e.g. videos, interviews, case studies) 	Engage innovators in the STADIEM Open Calls, Pushing innovative solutions forward and leverage them in the community / exploitation context
Group: Business incubators and accelerators			
Incubators, Accelerators, Investors / Corporates	<i>Benefit from NGM related solutions and new business models, liaise with SMEs and start-ups and innovators from other relevant domains, exploit the incubation and acceleration framework and programme</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Invitation to participate in workshops > Engage at specific events/workshops and exhibitions > Targeted publications and online communication > Project results in various forms 	Promote successful innovators among potential investors and support startups and SMEs in bringing their innovative solutions to pilot
Group: Civil society			
Public, users, audiences, NGOs	<i>Inform for project advancements, best practices, outcomes, liaise with NGM stakeholders, awareness</i>	> Engage at specific events/workshops and exhibitions	Raise awareness of EC funding dedicated to

	<i>on social aspects of incubation and acceleration programmes, liaise with start-ups and innovators</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Targeted publications and online communication > Project results in various forms 	European innovators
Group: Policy makers, regulators and public authorities			
Actors committed to support the development of the full economic potential of Europe	<i>Make informed strategic decisions and plan targeted activities, investments and calls on NGM for the good of our economies and societies</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Promote the outputs of the project and 3rd party projects in various forms > Amplify knowledge transfer (e.g., participation to working groups and policy debates) > Participation to dedicated policy events 	<p>Inform EU and national policy about media innovation needs, challenges and bottlenecks</p> <p>Promote innovations uptake through public procurement</p>
Group: Non-media sectors / verticals			
Representatives from non-media sector (health, education, etc.)	<i>Inform for project and NGM advancements, best practices, use cases, outcomes, liaise with local, EU and global initiatives, liaise with policy makers</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Invitation to participate in workshops > Engage at specific events/workshops and exhibitions > Targeted publications and online communication 	Inclusion of sectors in need of media services in the community, thus enriching scopes and exploitation opportunities
Group: Researchers and Academy			
Researchers from industry and academy	<i>Benefit and leverage upon the results, new suggested solutions and experiments, publications, and networking, share achievements within NGM community to facilitate know-how and technology transfer and link research results to specific use case and domains / verticals / applications</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Invitation to participate in workshops > Engage with at selected scientific events to voice them > Amplify knowledge transfer (e.g. publication repository; participation to working groups) 	Engage researchers and academics to stimulate further research, applications and partnerships opportunities with STADIEM ecosystem and innovators
Group: Standardisation bodies / initiatives			

Standardization organisations, working groups, research groups, pre-standardisation groups	<i>Support technology transfer, liaising with private sector, innovators, researchers, policy makers, share / promote standards and relevant strategies and success stories</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Invite to participate in the project events > Engage with at selected relevant events > Amplify / promote knowledge transfer towards standardization bodies and open-source communities 	Long-term sustainability through the standardisation field
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2.3 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGIC APPROACH

➡ Stage 1 - Awareness creation and marketing foundation (M01-M06)

STADIEM is currently in this phase – The measures described below are either already in place or in progress.

Scope: designing the dissemination, communication, and community building strategy and plan, including refinement and mapping of target groups and selection of dedicated communication tools and community building activities, and to inform all relevant stakeholders about the STADIEM scope and objectives. This phase is also being dedicated to defining the liaisons and interaction mechanisms with the rest of the domain entities and players, including relevant key stakeholders from the defined target groups and the relevant innovation activities, including the IA and CSA funded under the ICT-44-2020. The 1st Open Call is situated in this phase (February 2021), requiring adequate promotion.

Measures: The STADIEM website D5.1, the Outreach and impact creation strategy and plan D5.2, the community building strategy (D1.1), the Community map and database (D1.2), a dedicated calendar of events, a project introduction flyer, a project presentation (slides), dedicated social media channels established, participation to at least one conference presenting the STADIEM concept and the first edition of the STADIEM e-newsletter circulated. The 1st Open Call is being already promoted through a social media campaign, which will be further enforced by a specific webinar (with a dedicated promotion) after the launch.

➡ Stage 2 - Community outreach and engagement bootstrap (M07-M12)

Scope: to actively reach out the main target stakeholders to generate interest in STADIEM activities and outcomes focusing on the Open Calls and Incubation Programme promotion and set a solid foundation for the planned dissemination activities. Stakeholders will also be reached out to provide support for the promotion of the project thanks to close collaboration of all WP3 tasks. Planning for first events participation and organization, including the first workshops in collaboration with the WP1, the OC1 kick-off event, OC1 webinars.

Measures: slide-based presentations of first project results, a first video to be used to raise awareness, animation of social media channels, a number of news items pushed out via the STADIEM website and media, newsletters, and participation in selected events, to promote the project and 3rd party project activities of the Open Call 1, organization of engagement of workshops.

➤ Stage 3 - STADIEM global outreach (M13-M36)

Scope: to actively engage and support the adoption and deployment of the concepts and tools offered by STADIEM through dedicated promotional activities. This includes online publications, development, and distribution of promo materials, deliverables, participation to selected events, organization of OC2 kick-off workshop (WP4), organization of dedicated OCs closing workshops - DemoDays (WP4), exhibitions and liaisons with relevant initiatives, organization of 2 OC2 webinars, organization of a final project DemoDay event. Besides identifying the potential results and outcomes of the project for showcasing, STADIEM also identified some potential national and international events already listed in the next paragraphs.

Measures: promotional material in various forms, publications, established liaisons with relevant initiatives, a number of news items pushed out via the project's website and media channels, including press releases, technical reports, additional editions of the e-newsletter, interviews, videoclips, dedicated webinars, participation to events, infographics presenting results and lessons learned from the Impact Assessment activities (Task 5.2), and the Programme assessment activities under WP4.

Figure 1 gives an overview of these phases.

FIGURE 1: STADIEM IMPACT CREATION APPROACH

2.4 SUSTAINABLE COMMUNICATION IN TIME OF COVID-19

The STADIEM dissemination and communication approach takes into account the sustainability principles for the organization of events and the production of communication materials, considering the challenges and limitations created by the COVID-19 pandemic. For this purpose, we will:

- Organize virtual meetings and workshops instead of face-to-face events (e.g., Mid-February 2021 1st Open Call webinar to promote the call and inform stakeholders)
- Avoid using material resources where possible (e.g., avoid printing flyers when unnecessary and instead promote the online download, produce promotional materials using recycled materials, and avoid single-use products)
- Encourage the reduction of emissions through sustainable mobility practices (e.g., recommend bicycle use, public transport at STADIEM events and reward such actions)
- Work with suppliers (printers, caterers, etc.) that use sustainable products and materials

- Try to measure the carbon footprint and compensation of emissions of partners' traveling to dissemination events
- Involve partners directly into remote gathering of footage for video production, or use of animation, when shooting on certain location is not possible

3 OUTREACH AND IMPACT CREATION AT M04

3.1 PROJECT'S BRAND IDENTITY

As an EC co-funded Innovation Action project, a clear project brand identity needs to be implemented in order to establish a consistent visibility in our communication and dissemination activities.

The recognition and perception of a brand is highly influenced by its visual presentation. A project's visual identity is the overall look of its communications. Effective visual brand identity is achieved by the consistent use of particular visual elements to create distinction, such as specific fonts, colors, and graphic elements.

The visual identity and sets of guidelines have been finalized in the early stages of the project to secure a strong and unique brand. It will be incorporated in all promotional and dissemination materials produced during the project and will be used by all project partners in their communication activities.

FIGURE 2: STADIEM LOGO

The main font families chosen are "Encode Sans" (free and Open source) and "Arial": both suitable for print, screen, web, and titling usages. The "Encode Sans" font, combined with "Arial" make a contemporary and neat font combination with detailed one-stroke forms. The clear letters illustrate strong but dynamic lines, and an innovation touch. For deliverables and reports the "Arial" font has been chosen, being a default font in most operative systems, to maximize compatibility.

The color palette (figure below), is composed of 4 colors based on the logo color scheme, inspiring innovation, media, technology and connection, to which 2 grey tones are added for variation and grayscale material necessities. This is intended as the primary color palette of all STADIEM materials.

Palette of corporate colors

FIGURE 3: STADIEM COLOUR PALETTE

Martel Innovate prepared a document that provides guidelines (see Annex A at the end of the document) to create a unique and easily recognizable image footprint. Such guidelines define all of the basic graphic characteristics of STADIEM, from the logo, the color palette to the fonts used. The STADIEM logo is shown in several variations, to be used depending on the background, and in different sizes, to guarantee readability in different sources, e.g., reports, web, presentations. The range of colors to be used in the project are the ones adopted in the logo. Each color is defined with precise printing characteristics (CMYK) and digital encoding (RGB and HEX).

A **PowerPoint presentation template** was created to be used by the partners to create their presentations for all external and internal events, meetings, etc., based on a common look and feel.

FIGURE 4: STADIEM PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

A Word document template was created to be used by the partners for deliverables (this document follows the defined template).

FIGURE 5: STADIEM DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

Finally, a **mascot character** was created to be the “face” of STADIEM across media (See Figure 6). The mascot not only guides the visitor throughout the project’s website but also serves as a sort of “testimonial” in social media campaigns, appearing in situations aimed to represent STADIEM-connected themes and messages to convey, in a nutshell.

FIGURE 6: STADIEM MASCOT

3.2 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Several internal communication tools have been adopted, in order to keep partners at once informed on processes in detail and able to keep track of tasks and deadlines easily. The aim is to have everyone up to speed and able to access required assets, without unnecessary information overload: to this purpose, file exchange via repository is encouraged, and apps such as Trello and Slack were selected to establish efficient communication sub-circles and clear overviews on to-do lists and work in progress.

- ➔ **Mailing list:** stadiem@lists.lab.vrt.be was set up for general internal communication.
- ➔ **Gdrive repository**, which was selected to act as the main venue to archive and internally exchange all projects files (including reporting documents, presentations and graphic assets)

FIGURE 7: STADIEM GDRIVE REPOSITORY

- **Slack:** Slack-based chats were created to facilitate direct messaging– Some chats are also dedicated to communications with the project’s Advisory Board and others will be dedicated to actors involved in the open call programme.

FIGURE 8: STADIEM SLACK CHATS

- **Trello board:** Trello has been adopted for specific communication of WP tasks, thus also creating an instant overview of internal collaboration. The partners aim to regularly update the cards in the boards, after internal meetings especially, to keep track of the work in progress.

FIGURE 9: STADIEM TRELLO BOARD

3.3 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

3.3.1 STADIEM WEBSITE

FIGURE 10: STADIEM WEBSITE HOMEPAGE

The project’s website www.stadiem.eu was launched at M02 and it has been described in detail in Deliverable *D5.1 STADIEM Website*. Listed below are the integrations made since the deliverable has been submitted and some initial analytics on the traffic generated. The website has been extended with:

- Open Call section
This section offers the visitor an FAQ on open calls, submission materials, link to partner F6S’s application form to enroll in open calls, as well as a link to a specific e-mail address for open call inquiries (opencalls@stadiem.eu)
- Key stakeholders questionnaires (Corporate and Investors sections)

Some initial results show the website has already counted 83 unique visitors, who generated 138 page views, as shown in Figure 11.

FIGURE 11: STADIEM WEBSITE ANALYTICS

The website is also home to **STADIEM’s News**: among the articles already published, reports on achievements aside, the news section features an ongoing series telling the story of

STADIEM's partners - After the Open Calls selection process, articles will be dedicated to present call winners and what they bring to the table.

3.3.2 STADIEM Social Media Channels

Various social networks were established as **marketing tools** to promote activities and outputs of the project on a regular basis, while also encouraging a wider discussion on the topics related to NGM activities. Thus, STADIEM created an active presence on the most popular social media channels used by our stakeholders, such as Twitter and LinkedIn, which are linked to the project's website. The partners were encouraged to define and share the best channels by which to access the appropriate target audiences.

A first major activity already conducted on STADIEM's social media consists of a **countdown campaign for the launch of the 1st Open Call**, as detailed in Section 4.7.1.

Below we present a brief overview of the social media channels created for STADIEM.

➔ Twitter

Twitter is a very dynamic social network that covers the news in real-time at a global level. STADIEM has established its Twitter account @STADIEMproject before the official start of the project (September 2020). At the time of writing, it counts **71 followers**, it has tweeted 28 posts, and has been already used to cover the project's own kick-off meeting and relevant initiatives and projects' activities.

The Twitter account will be used for **promoting and disseminating** the development of STADIEM, including news, events, outcomes, etc. Moreover, re-tweets will be made of relevant and interesting content from disparate sources. Last but not least, by following relevant users, STADIEM not only gains access to more relevant content and updates but also acquires more followers.

STADIEM uses Twitter to establish meaningful connections with an **active and relevant audience (EC, policy makers, industry stakeholders, local authorities and general public)**. These connections can produce opportunities for the project across the network of stakeholders. It also serves as a tool to tell everybody in real time what is happening in the co-creation workshops and other activities of the project.

FIGURE 12: STADIEM TWITTER ACCOUNT

➤ **LinkedIn**

LinkedIn is currently the main business network in the world and has more than 150 million users in more than 200 countries and territories.

STADIEM’s LinkedIn company page has been established before the project officially started (September 2020) to connect with investors, corporates, incubators etc. It counts, at the time of writing, **65 followers** and 15 posts have been published.

FIGURE 13: STADIEM LINKEDIN ACCOUNT

➤ **YouTube**

YouTube is one of the leading video-sharing platforms at a global level that allows to upload videos and create a community of subscribers. STADIEM will maintain a YouTube channel, used to disseminate STADIEM’s vision, concepts, and objectives, but also to promote and ensure enhanced visibility of the experts and engaged stakeholders of the project that participate in interviews and project events.

At the time of writing, a first video, created by project partner Next Media Accelerator to present their current startup batch, has been uploaded onto the channel.

FIGURE 14: STADIEM YOUTUBE CHANNEL

3.3.3 STADIEM newsletter

An e-Newsletter will be produced by the STADIEM consortium on a tri-monthly basis and will provide regular updates on trends of NGM practices, project results, partner news and upcoming events. As such, a typical e-newsletter of the project will contain highlights (major outcomes, links, contacts, and dissemination activities), the most important news, announcements, and a schedule of the major upcoming events. Mailings with invitations to relevant workshops and webinars, consultations and other information that cannot wait for the newsletter publication or that cannot appear only in the newsletter will be sent out regularly to the same database used for the newsletter. Project partners will provide information for the e-Newsletter and ensure that the content is accurate. The first issue of the newsletter will be published at the beginning of February 2021 (M5). Newsletters will be uploaded on the website and an internal calendar will be shared with all project partners for receiving their contributions and the final approval about the content and appearance.

A mailing list has been created, based on subscription, giving the possibility to share the e-newsletter via mass mailing as well to inform interested users about project news, achievements, and planning of events. A registration functionality allowing the interested visitors to subscribe to the newsletter is already available on the STADIEM website. It will be ensured that all these actions comply with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The design of the newsletter has already been developed (see Figure 14) and it provides a clear branding and content template, flexible enough for the communication needs.

FIGURE 15: STADIEM NEWSLETTER PREVIEW

3.3.4 STADIEM press releases and press coverage

Press releases will be edited on a regular basis and will coincide with key project achievements (e.g., organization of a large event, implementation of key activities within the project, etc.).

Press releases will be published in national and European media, thus contributing to the wider dissemination of the project. All partners will be responsible for engaging with their local media outlets to ensure a wider reach. All press releases will be published on the project's website.

At the time of writing, a first press release has already been issued for the occasion of the project's kick-off meeting and announcing the upcoming Open Call.

The upcoming planned press releases continue to promote the 1st Open Call, announcing its launch and, subsequently, winners.

All press releases will be collected in the dedicated area of STADIEM's website:
<https://www.stadiem.eu/press-releases/>

4 OUTREACH AND IMPACT CREATION PLAN

In this section the dissemination and communication activities and plan are described. This includes online and offline communication, events, promotional materials, and dedicated activities aiming at promoting the STADIEM open calls. Furthermore, Section 4.6 offers an overview of the community building and the liaison activities with relevant projects and initiatives (formally carried out in WP1 *Community of Ecosystems*) that are relevant and interconnected with the STADIEM communication and dissemination plan. This section ends with an overview of the exploitation strategy.

4.1 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Communication will ensure both ad hoc and regular updates to be pushed out. The online communication will be articulated as follows:

Website & Website promotion

STADIEM's website will enhance the visitors' experience, providing a one-stop shop for promotion of the project activities. In particular, the following actions have already been implemented:

- Create and share an editorial calendar with all partners to guide our communication with the community, based on their needs and our offering, as well as maintain a consistent schedule of news articles (eg. direct engagement of partners in the communication efforts allows us to create a section on the website with testimonials and partner introductions).
- Encourage partners to submit their project's news to the STADIEM website for republishing to the broader audience. This will strengthen the relevance of the website as well as increase the reach and impact of the news.
- Encourage partners to repost news of direct and indirect interest from partners and the general media. This shows that STADIEM is involved and engaged in the larger world. If possible, this content should be posted with added commentary that demonstrates expertise and adds value to the article.
- Organize and aggregate news articles by topic and relevance to improve the ability to share e.g., via social channels, especially when dealing with calls to action such as events and open calls. This allows each project to maximize the value of its communication outreach.

Social media

To ensure a robust and prominent presence within our targeted audiences' social media sphere, STADIEM will:

- Create and share a social media publishing schedule that identifies optimal times for publishing project information on social media, as well as indicating offset times for resharing partners and relevant projects/initiatives social content. Through this, each partner can publish their social content at the most appropriate time while ensuring that the network shares and amplifies it to the best extent.
- This amplification is achieved by ensuring that all partners follow each other on social media, and reshare content with commentary regularly. To maximize the value of the reshares, STADIEM will provide offset windows to each partner. For example, if a post is

made on a Tuesday morning, some partners' offsets will ask for sharing that afternoon, while some will be asked to share the next morning or afternoon. In this way, the message is shared widely and reinforced, instead of saturating the channels at one time.

- ➡ Encourage project partners to actively monitor and share the STADIEM channels for content suitable for resharing, preferably with commentary. This will increase the reach and impact for each partner as well as the STADIEM community.
- ➡ Consolidate important calls to action, news articles and events posted to the STADIEM Editorial Plan and website and directly share them with partners

With different media channels, the reach is, by nature, differentiated. In general terms, we aim to use specific social media for the following specific target audiences:

TABLE 2 : SOCIAL MEDIA AND RESPECTIVE AUDIENCES

CHANNEL	AUDIENCE	ACTIVITY	FREQUENCY
Twitter	Partners, pundits, general audience	Short form copy to draw attention to another channel.	3 tweets per week 2-3 re-tweets/day
LinkedIn	Current and potential collaborators, SMEs, researchers	Framed, targeted stories for the general readership, group posts for technical specialists.	1 LinkedIn article of commentary/week Event content on an ad hoc basis
YouTube	All stakeholders	Event coverage and feature videos	Videos released on a per-event basis

Other social media platforms or online outlets (e.g., Instagram, TikTok, Medium etc.) could be considered, to explore next generation media further, and other types of audiences.

4.1.1 Guidelines for social media channels

All social media communications will be:

- ➡ Engaging. The content must be topical and engaging and inform the target stakeholders about the facts, as well as remind them what STADIEM is and aims for.
- ➡ Consistent. All content must be consistent and in line with the STADIEM positioning, content structuring, channels, and scheduling.

With respect to active communication via Twitter, specific attention will be paid to the choice of the most appropriate hashtags on a case-by-case basis (e.g., when posts focus on film-related media and events, hashtags and handles to be included will be selected to fit the topic). Hashtags can be a very useful tool for broadening the community and acquiring new followers. However, they need to be carefully chosen or they are just wasting character count.

A hashtag that is too broad means our message will be lost in the noise. For example, if we use #media, we are going to be instantly buried under mass media communications.

On the other hand, hashtags that are too specific mean that we will only be visible to people who are already aware of the project. For example, #PROJECTNAME will only be visible to those who are already aware. STADIEM uses Twitter to establish meaningful connections with an active and relevant audience (EC, policy makers, media stakeholders, innovators, general public). These connections can produce beneficial opportunities for the project across the network of stakeholders. It also serves to tell everybody in real time what is happening in the co-creation workshops and other activities of the project. The credentials for Twitter are the following:

- @STADIEMproject - Twitter handle, mentions the project
- #STADIEM – hashtag
- #NextGenerationMedia – hashtag
 - Examples of appropriate hashtags:
 - #NGM
 - #H2020
 - #innovation
 - #socialmedia
 - #DigitalEU
 - NextGenerationEU
 - #startupscaling
 - #startupexits
 - #scaleups

To maximize the impact of the project on social media channels, images and GIFs will be created and shared with all the partners. Tweets can be directed to specific accounts using @TWITTER-HANDLE in tweets. Here below are the lists of the project partners' Twitter handles or hashtags (in case they have no Twitter account) and the list of the European Union related Twitter accounts and hashtags. They are to be mentioned in the STADIEM Twitter account to generate conversations and interactions whenever is possible.

List of the European Union related Twitter accounts and hashtags:

- @EU_H2020 #H2020 shall be included in our tweets to maximize their visibility
- @NGI4EU
- @DSMeu
- @EU_Commission
- @NetTechEU
- @StartUpEU
- @Etp4HPC
- @STARTSEU
- @FETFX_EU

List of STADIEM supporters and project's partners:

- @MediaMotorEU
- @AI4Europe
- @NGI4EU
- @martel_innovate

- @VRTSandbox
- @VRT
- @MediaCityBergen
- @Storytek
- @NMA_vc
- @EBU_HQ
- @f6s
- @public_spaces
- @nycmedialab
- @mdf_cannes
- @IndustryTallinn
- @5GPPP
- @BDVA_PPP
- @wef
- @Eudat_eu
- @IoT_EPI
- @5gmediahub
- @exitacademy
- @exitsexist
- @eu_lighthouse
- @FutureTechEU
- @NGI_Explorers
- @edincubator
- @mediaroad_eu
- @softlanding_eu
- @memadproject

4.2 PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

4.2.1 Flyers, Posters, Merchandising

Project flyers will be created and used for informing interested people about the project's objectives and activities. Upon completion, the flyers will be uploaded to the STADIEM website and shared as printed versions during relevant events.

Moreover, **roll-ups** will be created, matching the look and feel of the website and the overall project design concept to meet the needs of the project.

Posters of a smaller size (A0) will be produced. STADIEM will also consider producing event focused posters of smaller size if considered necessary, where the content of the poster will be replaced to fit the needs (theme) of the event.

Both the roll-up and the posters will be prepared in English (local languages to be considered if appropriate or necessary) to raise awareness of the stakeholders and a variety of relevant audiences about the project with succinct textual and graphical information.

Printable versions of the posters will also be created and provided to partners to be printed and used at the events they participate in.

The design will be easily adjustable to the requirements individual partners have, in case an additional or a more specific version is required.

The project logo, the EU flag, and acknowledgment along with the STADIEM website and the social media links will be displayed on all promotional materials.

4.2.2 Videos

STADIEM will produce and release about four videos per year to present the project and its achievements. Videos will promote specific aspects of STADIEM, as well as partners' activities. An Open Call webinar recording will be among the first videos produced in 2021.

4.3 PLANNED WORKSHOPS AND EVENTS

➤ Four joint Hubs Workshops for the kick-off and closing of the Open Calls

- The first workshop will be in Year 1 in M5 (Mid-February 2021), immediately following the launch of the STADIEM Open Call #1.
- The second workshop will be in Year 2 in M16 just after the launch of the STADIEM Open Call #2 and may also include updates on the development phase of the Call #1 as well as lessons learned during the ongoing Call #1.
- The third workshop will be in Year 2 in M22 to mark the closing of Call #1 to discuss the outcomes of Call #1 with relevant stakeholders.
- The fourth workshop will be in Year 3 in M34 following the conclusion of the pilot phase under Call #2.

These workshops will address different categories of stakeholders (see Section 2.2) including traditional media operators, media producers, technologists and technology innovators, SMEs and start-ups, business incubators and accelerators, to interact together and match the needs of the media sector with innovative solutions sustained by appropriate funding opportunities.

The first workshop will be held online due to restrictions of the COVID19 pandemic. Hopefully, the following ones will be held in presence during events. Opportunities of possible co-location of workshops together with other large events for the second, third and fourth workshop will be explored.

➤ Four Webinars on specific topics

The webinars will be promoted across the wide community of stakeholders identified under Task 1.1 Community Building Strategy and community management through the channels mentioned in Section 4.6 of this document. The scope of the webinars is to inform innovative start-ups of the objectives and conditions of participation to the STADIEM Open Calls and their outcomes.

- The first webinar will be in Year 1 in M5 and it will present STADIEM project, disseminating information related to the launch of the 1st Open Call. A 1.5/2hs. time slot has been planned, introducing in its program objectives, eligibility criteria, and guidelines of the call.
- The second webinar shall take place towards the end of 2021, providing a stage for the selected start-ups from the 1st Open Call, promoting their innovation. The

discussion and organization around the second webinar will take place in the second half of 2021.

- The third and fourth webinars will take place in correspondence with the launch of the 2nd Open Call.

➔ Final project Demo Day

The Final project Demo Day will be held in M36 and will showcase the resulting products developed and piloted by funded start-ups under the two STADIEM open calls.

A decision on the format of the Demo Day, location of the event and/or possible colocation with a bigger event is planned to be made in the first half of Year 3.

4.4 PRESENTATIONS OR TALKS

Table 2 below presents the initial plan of events and conferences where STADIEM project could be presented in the future. Some of them have already been confirmed and partners are preparing their presentations and defining the participation's details. Due to the COVID pandemic, the planning of these events is closely monitored, and the consortium will evaluate the most interesting venues to promote STADIEM.

TABLE 3 : RELEVANT EVENTS M5-M36

EVENT	DATE, LOCATION	TYPE OF AUDIENCE	APPROX. AUDIENCE SIZE	ACTIVITIES	LEAD PARTNER
EBU Digital Radio Summit	17 February 2021, Online	Broadcasting industry	200	Presentations, workshops	EBU
EFM Start-ups (during European Film Market)	1-5 March 2021, Berlin, Germany	Corporates, Startups	10,000	Meetings, Networking, Presentations	Storytek
Berlin Film Festival (Industry Event)	1-5 March 2021, Berlin, Germany	Media industry professionals, International journalists, General public	700,000	Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
SXSW Interactive	16-20 March 2021, Online	Corporates, industry, investors, Startups	20,000	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek, VRT, NMA

Arctic15	17-18 March 2021, Stockholm, Sweden	Investors, Startups, Corporates	3,000	Meetings, Networking, Presentations	Storytek
EBU Broadthinking	23-24 March 2021, Online	Broadcasting industry	200	Presentations, workshops	EBU
NMA Virtual Media Match	Spring 2021, Online	Media industry professionals, Investors, European start-up community, Founders	150-250	1:1 Matchmaking sessions with investors, media executives, startups	NMA
Collision	20-22 April, Online	Investors, Start-ups, Corporates	32,000	Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
International Conference on Mass Media and Education	22-23 April 2021, Boston, USA	Academics, Researchers	200	Presentations	TBD
Latitude59	27-28 May 2021, Tallinn, Estonia	Investors, Start-ups	5,000	Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
World Conference on Media and Mass Communication	17-19 June 2021, Cagliari, Italy	Media industry professionals, Researchers, Academics, International journalists	250	Presentations, workshops	TBD
Cannes NEXT Media Innovation Platform (Cannes Marché Du Film)	6-15 July 2021, Cannes, France	Corporates, industry	10,000	Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
sSTARTUp Day	25-27 August, Tartu, Estonia/Online	Investors, Startups, Corporates	5,000	Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek

DLD Tel Aviv	11-14 October 2021, Tel Aviv, Israel	Investors, Corporates	5,000	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
Scoopcamp	Fall 2021, Online/Hybrid	Media industry professionals, International journalists, Media innovators	250	Panels, Discussions, Keynotes	NMA
Online Marketing Rockstars	Fall 2021, Hamburg, Germany/Online	Digital marketers, Digital natives, Online marketing community	1000-2000	Master classes	NMA
IBC Conference	10-13 September 2021, Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Media, Entertainment and Technology Industry	50,000	Trade fair, Presentations, Networking	TBD
NABshow	10-13 October 2021, Las Vegas, USA	Media, Entertainment and Technology Industry	90,000	Trade fair, Presentations, Networking	TBD
International Conference on Mass Media and Education	28-29 October 2021, Los Angeles, USA	Academics, Researchers	200	Presentations	TBD
Industry @ Tallinn & Baltic Event	10-27 November 2021, Tallinn, Estonia	Media industry professionals, International journalists	800	Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
Slush	2021	Investors, Startups, Corporates	20,000	Networking, Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek

Webit	2021	Investors, Startups, Corporates	15,000	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
NGI Forum	2021	Researchers, Academics, Policy makers, Industry, Startups, SMEs	700	Presentations, workshops	Martel
MCB tech conference	2021, Bergen, Norway	Media industry professionals	200	Presentations, workshops	Media City Bergen
AIOTI Signature event	2021	Industry, Researchers, Academics, Policy makers	250	Presentations	Martel
EBU Metadata Developer Network (MDN) workshop	2021	Industry	200	Presentations, workshop	EBU
EBU/ASBU Week of Technology	2021	Industry	200	Presentations, workshop	EBU
DLD Munich	2021, Munich, Germany/Hybrid	Investors, Corporates	5,000	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
EFM Start-ups (during European Film Market)	2022	Corporates, Startups	10,000	Meetings, Networking, Presentations	Storytek
Latitude59	2022	Investors, Start-ups	5,000	Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
Cannes NEXT Media Innovation Platform (Cannes	2022	Corporates, industry	10,000	Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek

Marché Du Film)					
SXSW Interactive	2022	Corporates, industry, investors, startups	20,000	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek, VRT, NMA
sSTARTUp Day	2022	Investors, Startups, Corporates	5,000	Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
Arctic15	2022	Investors, Startups, Corporates	3,000	Meetings, Networking, Presentations	Storytek
DLD Tel Aviv	2022, Tel Aviv, Israel	Investors, Corporates	5,000	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
DLD Munich	2022, Munich, Germany	Investors, Corporates	5,000	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
Slush	2022	Investors, Start-ups, Corporates	20,000	Networking, Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
Collision	2022	Investors, Start-ups, Corporates	32,000	Presentations, Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
Webit	2022	Investors, Start-ups, Corporates	15,000	Stakeholders engagement	Storytek
ICDBIT 2022: Digital Broadcasting and Interactive Television Conference	21-22 January 2022, Amsterdam, The Netherlands	Media industry professionals, Researchers, Academics	250	Presentations, workshops	TBD

4.5 SPECIALIZED PRESS

STADIEM also plans to target specific publications, relevant to its area of interest and stakeholders to promote the work carried out by STADIEM and the innovators' participation to Open Calls. The following outlets will be considered:

- Startup trade publications (i.e. EU Startups, Techcrunch, Wired, Recode, etc.)
- Relevant media / filmtech press (i.e., Hollywood Reporter, Screen International, CineEuropa, Variety etc.)
- Tech integration media – (i.e., TVB Europe, etc.)
- Larger innovation media (i.e., Maize magazine)

4.6 SYNERGIES AND LIASONS WITH RELATED PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

Thanks to the participation of many partners in several ongoing projects, associations, initiatives, and the Incubators and Accelerators networks targeted liaisons and synergies will be leveraged to ensure STADIEM's broad outreach, fostering effective STADIEM uptake and validation of the Incubation Programme without excluding any other relevant to the overall Calls ambition.

TABLE 4 : STADIEM LIAISONS WITH PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

PROJECT TITLE	SHORT DESCRIPTION	FOCUS AND LINK WITH STADIEM
<u>Next Generation Internet</u>	The Next Generation Internet (NGI) initiative aims to shape the development of the Internet of tomorrow towards an Internet of humans that responds to people's fundamental needs, including trust, security, and inclusion, and reflects the values and the norms that we enjoy in Europe.	Common technological challenges and audiences (innovators, academics etc) Participation to NGI events (NGI Conference / NGI Forum)
<u>NGI Explorers</u>	The NGI Explorers Programme vision is to leverage the EU-US researchers exchange and foster "made in Europe" NGI products and services, through the engagement of Internet researchers in understanding different perspectives, vision, values, and technology approach, for an uplifted research mindset.	STADIEM will leverage F6S' knowledge in engaging and supporting high-tech researchers and start-ups in the NGI technologies. F6S is also an established NGI partner (coordinator of NGI

		Explorers and dissemination partner of NGI DAPSI).
<u>PublicSpaces</u>	The PublicSpaces initiative aims to claim back the internet for the common good. It is a coalition of EU broadcasters and other public organisations (museums, festivals, heritage organisations and universities) that share a vision of developing an ecosystem where digital technologies facilitate a user-driven ecosystem for broadcasting that is equitable and democratic, where rights are protected and where strong public institutions and private industry players function in the public interest.	Common challenges and audiences (innovators, academics etc.).
<u>StartUp Lighthouse</u>	The project lights the way for start-ups within Europe by organising 8 Deep Dive Weeks in 4 ecosystems: Berlin, Dublin, Lisbon and the Baltics – meeting over 1600 different ecosystem players in specific themes such as fintech, refugee tech, e-gov, IoT, etc - and culminating with a Top 10 Lighthouse Award in London each year.	STADIEM already takes benefit from this project, since F6S helps to finetune the project based on lessons learned from Startup-Lighthouse. Additionally, Stadiem benefits from the established network/ ecosystems.
<u>FETFx</u>	A CSA funded project of the FET-Open Programme which aims to orchestrate and amplify the FET Research and Innovation projects' communication efforts.	Contribution of multimedia contents for a multiplying effect.
<u>AI4EU</u>	An EU project focusing on building the European AI on demand platform.	Common challenges and audiences (innovators, academics etc.).
<u>NMA Batch 12 acceleration program</u>	The program is bound to accelerate and invest into early-stage media tech companies and to connect them to relevant stakeholders within the European media industry.	Shared network of relevant stakeholders and peer exchange between startup founders through

		potential activities and events
<u>MediaMotorEurope</u>	MediaMotorEurope is a project launching in January 2020 and run by several of the partners of this consortium (VRT, MCB and F6S). The project will help scaleups with deeptech solutions to scale their solutions which are addressing challenges facing the media sector.	STADIEM will ensure that any startups recruited in its programme and that have solutions that are relevant for MediaMotorEurope, will be helped to apply to the MME programme and linked to relevant resources in the MediaMotorEurope programme.
<u>EDIncubator</u>	The main objective of the EDIncubator project is to leverage the technology and knowledge on Big Data across countries and sectors thanks to the incubation of start-ups/SMEs who use Big Data open-source tools oriented to sort out major challenges in different businesses which facilitate their data assets.	STADIEM will be following the EDIncubator project closely to collect best practices on how to engage with corporates and connect these with technology and innovative Startups and SMEs. The experience of EDIncubator within the Big Data domain will be highly valuable for STADIEM goal associated with the integration of emerging technologies in the Media sector.
<u>MediaRoad</u>	Within the European MediaRoad project, the successful VRT Sandbox model has been transformed into a replicable model for other European broadcasters. Together with partners as the EBU, BBC and RAI, VRT has built a network for accelerators of media innovation: the Sandbox Hub. Entrepreneurs, start-ups, as well as SMEs with media-related concepts involving technology, journalism, social media and content, are able to apply for a project. Each Sandbox will operate independently but be interlinked across	STADIEM will leverage on the activities of the Sandbox hub, and will engage with the hub to expand the community and investigate sustainability opportunities.

	Europe through a platform to share success cases for broader implementation.	
<u>Soft Landing</u>	Soft-Landing connects smaller start-up ecosystems to the larger ones through building awareness and capacity for scaling and providing Soft-landing support.	F6S brings its experience on connecting ecosystems across Europe through missions but refines this into the STADIEM project. Network and ecosystem build will benefit STADIEM.
<u>MeMad</u>	An EU funded project that aims at better visualising data and relevant for anyone working with audiovisual content. It has specifically developed solutions to give better access to video for those that have visual or hearing impairments.	The resources developed for accessibility are directly relevant for any start-ups / scaleups coming through STADIEM. It offers a network of experts for mentoring, testing and validating.
<u>New York City Media Lab</u>	Founded in 2010, NYC Media Lab is dedicated to driving innovation and ultimately job growth in US media and technology by facilitating collaboration between universities and companies in the world capital of media. Comprised of a consortium including New York City Economic Development Corporation, School of Visual Arts, New York University, Columbia University, The New School, CUNY, IESE, and Pratt Institute, NYC Media Lab's goals are to generate research and development, knowledge transfer, and talent across all of the city's campuses.	As a global partner of the NYC Media Lab the NMA will ensure access and the exchange of knowhow for STADIEM, its partners and the selected European start-ups.
<u>Marché Du Film NEXT - Festival de Cannes</u>	Cannes Next, is a 6-day cutting edge showcase and business platform connecting world-class creativity with world-class innovation at the world's leading platform for moving images.	Showcasing the STADIEM program and beneficiaries.
<u>Industry@Tallinn & Baltic Event - Tallinn Black</u>	The mission of I@T&BE is to serve as a gateway for global audiovisual industries from and to the region as well as to establish ties and collaboration points with the ICT, gaming, mobile, technology and venture capital	As the partner and frequent innovation contributor, ST will ensure dissemination,

<u>Nights Film Festival</u>	sectors. I@T&BE is focusing on connecting the Baltic and Scandinavian film, entertainment, tech & VC professionals with the US, Asia, Europe, Russia and the CIS countries. Constantly widening its global reach, always addressing the most acute issues and with over 800 guests attending (among them 550 accredited industry professionals), it has grown into one of the largest media industry events in the region. As a result, Tallinn has regularly partnered with the European Commission, which has entrusted it to organize the European Film Forum conference that will see another edition in 2019.	promotion and know how activities for the STADIEM consortium and its beneficiaries at the annual Industry@Tallinn & Baltic Event summit.
<u>Digital Transformation Initiative</u>	The initiative offers unique insights into the impact of digital technologies on business and wider society over the next decade. DTI research supports collaboration between the public and private sectors focused on ensuring that digitalization unlocks new levels of prosperity for both industry and society.	Common challenges and audiences.
<u>5G PPP</u>	The 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G PPP) is a joint initiative between the European Commission and European ICT industry (ICT manufacturers, telecommunications operators, service providers, SMEs and researcher Institutions).	Common challenges and audiences, focus on ICT.
<u>European Cloud Initiative</u>	The initiative aims to strengthen Europe's position in data-driven innovation, improve its competitiveness and cohesion, and help create a Digital Single Market in Europe.	Common challenges and audiences, focus on competitiveness of European market.
<u>European Technology Platform for High-Performance Computing</u>	The European Technology Platform (ETP) for High-Performance Computing (HPC) - is a private, industry-led and non-profit association. Its main mission is to promote European HPC research and innovation in order to maximize the economic and societal benefit of HPC for European science, industry and citizens.	Common challenges and audiences, focus on competitiveness of European market.
<u>Big Data Value Association</u>	The mission of the BDVA is to develop the Innovation Ecosystem that will enable the data and AI-driven digital transformation in Europe delivering maximum economic and	Common challenges and audiences, focus on competitiveness of

	societal benefit, and achieving and sustaining Europe's leadership on Big Data Value creation and Artificial Intelligence.	European market and Big Data.
<u>European Data Initiative (EUDAT)</u>	EUDAT's vision is Data is shared and preserved across borders and disciplines. Achieving this vision means enabling data stewardship within and between European research communities through a Collaborative Data Infrastructure (CDI), a common model and service infrastructure for managing data spanning all European research data centers and community data repositories.	Common challenges and audiences.
<u>European AI Alliance</u>	AI Alliance has become a point of reference in stakeholder-driven discussions on AI policy. With over 4000 members and a daily exchange of discussions, documentation, and AI-related events from all over Europe, the AI Alliance is now directly contributing to the European debate on AI, and feeds into the European Commission's policymaking in this area.	Common challenges and audiences, broad range.
<u>STARTS Community</u>	S+T+ARTS is an initiative of the European Commission to foster alliances of science, technology and the arts, that effectively implement a European approach to technological innovation centered on human needs and values.	Common challenges and audiences, focus on the arts.
<u>IoT European Platforms Initiative</u>	The IoT-European Platforms Initiative (IoT-EPI) was formed to build a vibrant and sustainable IoT-ecosystem in Europe, maximizing the opportunities for platform development, interoperability and information sharing.	Common challenges and audiences (ecosystem creation, interoperability).
<u>Startup Europe</u>	Startup Europe is an initiative of the European Commission to connect high tech startups, scaleups, investors, accelerators, corporate networks, universities and the media.	Common challenges and audiences.
<u>5GMediaHUB</u>	This project aims to build and operate an elastic, secure, trusted, all-in-one, multi-tenant service execution and NetApps development environment based on an open	Common challenges and audiences (media services).

	cloud-based architecture and APIs, by developing and integrating a testing and validation system with existing well-established 5G testbeds, for enabling the fast prototyping, testing and validation of novel 5G media services and NetApps , thus reducing the entry barrier to 3rd party media application testers (from SMEs, service providers, researchers, etc.).	
Medianumeric	MediaNumeric provides students in Journalism and Communication studies theoretical know-how and skills needed to embolden them to take on opportunities that data-driven journalism brings. It covers key subjects: exploration of multimedia data, storytelling with multimedia data and tracking & debunking disinformation. The Alliance consists of leading actors in academia, industry and audiovisual archives. It analyses needs of the EU news ecosystem and ties them to the educational offer of HEIs.	Possibility to test STADIEM start-up solutions in journalism practice.
Accelerate Estonia	Accelerate Estonia is the world's well-known and most recognized national innovation program, that helps Estonia punch above its weight by experimenting, validating and solving wicked global problems and launching game changing success stories from the future for the future.	Possibility for Stadiem beneficiaries to pilot at a country wide to solve wicked problems in media / content.
Exits Exist	A monthly invite only platform on corporate – startup collaboration and development organized by the Exit Academy, Speedinvest and Techstarts.	Showcasing the Stadiem program and beneficiaries.

4.7 OPEN CALLS PROMOTION

The STADIEM Open Calls will be broadly advertised via the following channels and actions:

➞ Website

- Publication of the Open Call to STADIEM website and link to the F6S dedicated community space for submission

➞ Social Media (using dedicated promotional kit, including visuals/copy/link)

- Dissemination through STADIEM social channels, partners and community social channels

➤ Press release/specific announcement message/dedicated promotional kit (visuals/copy/link)

- Dissemination through NGI, FET, 5G PPP, FED4FIRE+ mailing list
- Promotion through the National Contact Points dedicated to Future Technologies
- Dissemination through communities and portals, such as Funding Box, Edgeryders etc.
- Publication of the Open Call to all relevant Media and NGI web sites and project websites
- Dedicated communication towards European global funds and investors interested in mediatech startups

➤ Online/offline events

- Flyer to be distributed online and offline at attended and organized events
- Focused presentations will be given through dedicated webinars and when possible at conferences and third parties workshops to promote the Open Call opportunity (1 for each open call)

4.7.1 1st Open Call promotional plan

The 1st Open Call will be launched on 1st February 2020. At the time of writing, a **promotional social media countdown campaign**, consisting of 3 digital illustrated cards designed for use on Twitter and LinkedIn, has been created and is in deployment (see Figure 16).

FIGURE 16: STADIEM 1ST OPEN CALL COUNTDOWN SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN

The promotion will be supported by an online webinar foreseen for Mid-February 2021 to present the call and answer participants' questions (as mentioned in Section 4.3). The webinar will be recorded, edited, and made available on the project YouTube channel. At the end of

the 1st Open Call cycle, STADIEM will organize a 2nd webinar (or workshop if the COVID-19 emergency subsidies).

Further promotion has been planned around the Open Call and the related webinar, in the form of a small adv campaign. The campaign deployment venues targeted are Twitter/FB/Google AdWords, and it will feature illustrations (and/or small animations, depending on timing and resources finally deployed).

4.8 SUSTAINABILITY, INNOVATION, AND TAKE-UP ACTIONS AND PLAN

In task 5.3, the Sustainability, innovation, and take-up actions and plan, a market and competition analysis will be conducted. Next Media Accelerator is in lead of this item and will fulfill it as planned for in M13 and M36 of the project time span. Its goal is to have a clear representation of the market structure, key players, and their needs.

This will be achieved by analyzing the STADIEM ecosystem (using value network models) in relation to the new workflows defined in the project.

Market barriers, new trends, and relevant segments of the media landscape and creative industries will be monitored, examined, and adapted to (using a SWOT analysis in order to see where STADIEM can have an impact). In the end, it will result in an Exploitation Plan for the STADIEM assets in relation to the market analysis, as well as in a value proposition.

D5.6, D5.7: Market analysis, exploitation and sustainability. The report on market conditions and growth trends, competitor analysis, identification of common business models and key enablers and barriers to growth, including also the first draft of the partners' exploitation plans. The final version is a report on exploitation and sustainability activities, including individual exploitation plans of the partners and plans for the joint exploitation and longer-term viability of the project's ecosystem and market platform. This item will be delivered in M18 and M 36 by NMA according to the deliverable 5.6, D.5.7.

5 IMPACT ASSESSMENT

STADIEM will develop a detailed impact assessment plan that will assess the project framework, tools, and engagement strategy. The impact assessment plan will be made available to the partners at M05 and implemented from M06 onwards as planned in the original project plan.

The impact assessment plan will be devised and implemented according to the KPI's presented in Section 1.3.2.4 of the original proposal and will consist of the following:

- Ecosystem impact on the European media sector and the call's objectives; STADIEM network, Hubs, Stakeholders, Startups, and Beneficiaries
- STADIEM Framework / Program impact to Open calls, Framework deployment, Pilots, and Multidimensional stakeholder feedback to the framework progress & deployment
- Dissemination impact on project's visibility and media coverage; social media; community development; and events & presentations

Building on the original proposal, the impact assessment plan will take account into:

- Assessment of the framework
- Startup/beneficiary related metrics (OKRs, qualitative and quantitative feedback to staging, experts, open calls etc.)
- Quantitative metrics on dissemination KPIs
- The relevance of the dissemination plan in meeting the objectives of the calls (and proposing pivots if deemed necessary)
- Qualitative feedback of the stakeholders to ensure clarity and impact of dissemination along with key target groups and stakeholders.

Along with the impact assessment, task leader Storytek will set forth tools and methodologies to monitor the progress in relevant criteria and action items as well as provide feedback to the project leader if deviations occur.

Furthermore, by implementing the STADIEM's Communication and Dissemination Plan we expect to communicate relevant outcomes to each of the target groups, as well as to attract their interest and generate engagement that will influence the overall impact of the project. To assess the impact of STADIEM, the Dissemination Plan includes appropriate metrics that can be categorized in:

- Quantitative indicators such as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and online metrics,
- Qualitative indicators such as a proactive community, press coverage and long-term influence.

These types of indicators are detailed in the following sections.

5.1 QUANTITATIVE INDICATORS

Table 5 below details the KPIs which have been set for the Dissemination & Communication Activities and the status at M04.

TABLE 5 : STADIEM DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION KPIS

MEASURE	INDICATORS	TARGET	MEANS OF VERIFICATION	ACHIEVED AT M04
Flyers, Posters, Roll-ups	N. of flyers N. of posters/roll-ups (by the end of the project)	> 6 > 4	Report of activities by partners	n.a.
Project website	Unique visitors per month (average per year)	> 1,500	Built-in website statistics tool	Online at M02 83 Unique visitors
Social networks	N. of followers on Twitter, N. of followers on LinkedIn (average of new followers yearly)	> 300 > 100	Built-in platform analytics tool	71 Followers Twitter 65 Followers LinkedIn
e-Newsletter (every 3 months)	N. of newsletters (by the end of the project)	12	Publication on website	1
Videos	N. of videos published on the STADIEM website and social media and average number of views	4 (videos per year), 100 views per video	YouTube analytics	n.a.
Workshops - at least 4 by the end of the project	Average number of participants per workshop	Between 80 and 100	Registration and attendance lists, reports, presentations	n.a.

Participation to events and presentations	Number of external events partners attended to promote the project	At least 6 per year	Reports, recording, presentations	n.a.
Webinars (4 by the project end, 2 per OC)	Average number of participants	At least 50	Registration and attendance lists, recording, reports, presentations	n.a.
One open final event - Demo Day	Average number of participants	200	Registration and attendance lists, recording, reports, presentations	n.a.

5.2 MILESTONES

The table below presents the milestones related to the outreach and impact creation activities.

TABLE 6 : STADIEM WP5 MILESTONES

MILESTONE NO	MILESTONE TITLE	WP	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
MS5	Match & Develop - 1 st cycle and impact assessment	WP4, WP5	M18	Impact creation and assessment report (D5.4) and Match and Develop phases report - the 1st cycle (D4.1) are published

5.3 QUALITATIVE INDICATORS

Additionally, other positive results cannot be easily measured since they cannot be quantified. Thus, to better measure the overall impact of the dissemination plan we will use the following qualitative indicators:

- Proactive online community. Social networks dissemination efforts will ensure an interesting outcome in terms of discussions, feedback and content sharing, and engagement.
- Press/media coverage. Distribution of press releases and publication of articles are geared to achieve press/media coverage about the project.
- Long-term influence. Sometimes the impact takes longer than just an immediate reaction.

Therefore, it is expected that the return of investment will only be apparent later on in the project. This will be considered when monitoring the impact of the project.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

As described in this deliverable, the first 4 months of the project have been very intense for the Dissemination and Communication team, which has been working to set up the processes and tools to drive the communication activities across several media and regions. STADIEM's multicultural and multidisciplinary team offers a wide network that will be leveraged in the communication activities. The upcoming Open Call launch and the related webinar will give us the opportunity to engage (online) a wider scientific and technical audience, raising the project's awareness. As described in Sections 4.3 and 4.4 we are at work to define the calendar of events to attend, STADIEM webinars programs, and their promotion. Last but not least, STADIEM work is relevant to several initiatives and to the debate around the technological, social, economic impact of new media technologies in Europe and beyond. STADIEM will therefore make sure that partners pay close attention to opportunities that contribute to the ongoing debate, leveraging the consortium experience and project's outputs. Reaching and engaging a wider audience (media and the general public) will require a different communication approach, in which we will focus on the key messages that address the societal value, innovation, new media solutions, support to European start-ups and SMEs.

All the partners showed already a high level of commitment to maximize the project's impact promoting the event through their own channels, presenting STADIEM at online events, contributing to the news publications, and animating the social media dialogue with the project's stakeholders. STADIEM's editorial calendar proved to be a useful tool to converge on stable news production and to give visibility to each partner's area of expertise and work within the project. We now aim to optimize and accelerate the process, in order to maximize our online reach, in convergence with relevant initiatives and projects.

The 1st Periodic Report (PPR), due at M12, will provide the details regarding the progress of the Dissemination & Communication Plan, the KPIs achieved, the events attended and organized, and the effectiveness of the online communication.

ANNEX A

WHAT IS A BRAND IDENTITY?

A brand identity allows you to recognize a consistent look and feel across all outlets (electronic and printed visual media). It defines how those who come into contact with the brand should perceive it and influences their opinion of the brand.

This document lists and explains the visual identity elements of the project STADIEM.

These are rules and values to help you create and compose visual designs using its identity.

Examples of STADIEM's brand identity across different outlets (Twitter and LinkedIn accounts):

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LOGO

Main version of the STADIEM logo with some basic recommendations.

Main version

Safe area

With added tagline

Icon version (for social media outlets)

Minimum size

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2

LOGO VARIATIONS

The main logo is also provided in the variations depicted here below, to allow readability over dark backgrounds or for black and white printing purposes.

Greyscale version

Negative version

Black&White version

LOGO VARIATIONS

The variations are also provided for the version with added tagline of the logo.

Greyscale version

Negative version

Black&White version

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DOS AND DONT'S

Basic instructions on how to use the main logo - and its variations - over different types of backgrounds.

Dos

Negative version on high contrasted background.

Main version on background assuring high contrast.

Don'ts

Not enough contrasted background.

Not enough contrasted background.

CORPORATE COLOURS

A main palette of 4 colours based on the logo colour scheme. These include the colours of the logo gradient. In combination with the main colours palette, two more greyscale colours can be used.

For slide presentations and deliverables: the colour of standard elements has been defined and locked in the respective templates, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments.

To change colours (icons or additional text), editors will find the corporate color palette in the templates.

Palette of corporate colors

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FONT TYPES

STADIEM's brand uses Google Fonts' open source font Encode Sans for headings (Condensed Black version) and body copy (Regular and Bold versions). The usage of other versions of the font is allowed. This applies to the website, presentations and all promotional materials.

For deliverables, the system font Arial (only Regular and Bold versions) should be used instead, to avoid missing font issues, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments. It could be used also for presentations in case the two brand fonts are missing.

Alternative body copy and headings (for deliverables and presentations)

Arial regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Arial bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Headings

(website, presentations, and all promotional materials)

Encode Sans Condensed black

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Body copy

(website, presentations, and all promotional materials)

Encode Sans regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Encode Sans bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

EC ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

All the EC funded projects should clearly show the acknowledgement to the EC fund in all Dissemination & Communication materials (e.g. flyers, posters, roll-ups, brochures, videos, webiste, etc). Below there are some examples of the elements to show in different positions.

Funded by the EU's Horizon2020 programme under agreement n° 957321

Funded by the EU's Horizon2020 programme under agreement n° 957321

STADIEM project is funded by the EU's Horizon2020 programme under Grant Agreement number 957321

STADIEM

CONTACTS

For any questions regarding the STADIEM graphic assets and the uses you would like to make of them, do not hesitate to contact Galileo Disperati from Martel Innovate:
galileo.disperati@martel-innovate.com

All STADIEM graphic assets, including this brand guidelines and the fonts, can be downloaded on the repository of the project.

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